

‘Sahadharmacārī’: Ethics in the Sītā-Rāma Relationship in Śrīmad Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa

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Abstract: This research reviews and reframes contemporary interpretations that compare and misinterpret Sītā, the protagonist of the Śrīmad Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa, through the lens of modern reality television. The concern of the article is that - many modern critiques are driven by a feminist agenda that overlooks the foundational ethics of the epic. By analysing the mutual understanding between Rāmā and Sītā, this paper explores the psychological and dhārmic aspects of their relationship, highlighting how their roles were grounded in shared responsibility and leadership rather than oppression. In this article – for a man-woman relationship in modern family and society, the example of the mutual understandings between Rāmā’s Sītā and Sītā’s Rāmā is taken as a template. This article will go in the direction of analysing the shortcomings in the previously published article through the lens of modern reality television. Then it will be eventually substantiated by detailing the psychological aspects that played a pivotal role in the relationship between Sītā and Rāmā in the Indian Epic Śrīmad Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa.

Keywords: Sītā, Feminism, Mutual Understanding, Srimad Valmiki Ramayana, Dharma.

Introduction

Srimad Valmiki Rāmāyaṇa is a historic event in the lineage of the nation - Bharat aka India. It is revered as Ādikāvyaṃ – meaning the first ever Epic written in Sanskrit. It bears originality and there are many testimonies that are scrutinized and validated continuously till today. Whether they are proven or not, it still gives a fairly equal chance for it, to have happened really in the past. With that idea in mind, the character portrayal of Sītā Mātā, given by the author-writer, Madina, E. (2023) in her article titled as “Mythology and Reality TV: storytelling and feminist agency in the Rāmāyaṇa and *The Real Housewives*” comparing Sītā’s ordeals to that of the problems of today’s housewives is negated with some necessary arguments in this article. It is not adequate to take the support of only those versions of Rāmāyaṇa that are feminist driven. More so, the author calls them as Sitayana (Madina, E., 2023). Such views are often arbitrary, relying on feminist-driven versions of the narrative rather than the original Valmiki text. This article demonstrates how Rāmā revered Sītā and how Sītā’s decisions were rooted in rational agency and the preservation of *Dharma*. What is the need for such a negation to be done? It is indeed essential as today’s world is moving more towards the negative implications of hyper-independence – a term that is becoming more common in men as well as women rather than co-existence. But with these changing times, moral values have not changed. Both mid-life men and women seem to have lost the knack of learning values from the mouth and ways of their elder generations. *It is not an accusation, but a concern for a society’s healthy relationships - an actual alarming need of the hour.*

Convenient selection of phrases to misinterpret Sītā’s identity

First, all the points that the author Madina, E. (2023) claims to be the sufferings of Sītā Mata are carefully jotted down and analysed.

- Prince Rāmā eventually pronounces her impure and rejects her. (Madina, E., 2023).
- Kamala Subramaniam writes that pain is ‘the predominant emotion in the Rāmāyaṇa’. (Madina, E., 2023).

- Sītā begins the Rāmāyana young and defined by her husband and later ends it in emancipated stage of her life. (Madina, E., 2023).
- Having survived her pain and gained wisdom from it, she realises she has a choice: deciding to endure no longer and instead live for herself. (Madina, E., 2023).
- Sītā is initially presented in the Rāmāyana as the ‘Ur-Housewife’: she embodies *Nāri Dharm*, the ideal feminine code of conduct, showing endless dedication to her husband and society’s expectations. However, by the end of Sītā’s story and in many retellings, the notion of the perfect woman and wife is shattered. (Madina, E., 2023).

Sītā’s Rāmā

The Rāmā who had great reverence and intimate bonding with Sītā is seen through various incidents. The Rāmā that Sītā revered, was also giving back mutual love, affection and respect more than any man to a wife. How is this evident? It is seen in many incidents such as their conversations and behaviour while they spent their exclusive time in the exile away from all the crowd of the palace. In the forest, they were able to exchange their thoughts with each other. More than even a personal talk, Sītā and Rāmā did much of their duties like attending to the needs and requests of the panel of hermits/sages with whom they spent their major years in forest life. This is seen in many slokas in Araṇya Kānda of Vālmīki Rāmāyana.

Rāmā’s Sītā

Rāmā’s Sītā is indeed shown as a normal, contented woman. At the same time a dutiful, responsible wife as well as a strong-minded woman who had clarity on her duties. She is also portrayed as someone who realises that she is the wife of a Prince, bearing the responsibility of serving as a good example for the citizens. It cannot be mistaken as her pressure to be good. It is her conscious decision as a responsible leader. This was possible for her, because Rāmā also showed her the way of living, by being an example himself. Such a scenario cannot be misunderstood as a pressure on her. A CEO of a company or a leader of a nation voluntarily accepts his/her duties and responsibilities to achieve her status par excellence. Such a woman leader has the goal of satisfying the needs of a company or a country. All that physical and mental strain, pressure and wearing out, are they considered as her ill treatment?

Even to the extent of being put to the test of fire was like a moral agreement that Sītā had to sign with Rāmā for the welfare of the citizens under them. Yes, that came with the price of a mental agony, not just for Sītā but to Rāmā as well. Though the two kinds are not similar.

Rāmā’s qualities that inspired Sītā

ānṛśaṅsyaṅ parō dharmastvatṭta eva mayā śrutaḥ.

jānāmi tvāṅ mahāvīryaṅ mahōtsāhaṅ mahābalaṃ ॥¹

(‘O my supreme lord I know you are kind, righteous, valiant, vigorous, mighty. You are boundless, calm and deep like the ocean. You are lord of earth and the seas and compeer of Vasava. I have heard from you that motiveless compassion is the best way to make one righteous). Here, Sītā expresses that SriRāmā had many great qualities to exhibit – one such is being compassionate towards all beings.

Sītā as a responsible partner – It was not a torment!

In a context in Araṇya Kānda, Sītā mentors Rāmā when she insists him to

protect the sages in the forest from the clutches of the demons, during their exile period. She in fact, reminds Rāmā of his duties as a Prince, even though banished from the kingdom of Ayodhya. How can he forget the promise that he had given to the sages in the beginning of his exile period? She prompts him, not only to spend some happy times with her, but also to look at the big picture of the world and the protection of innocent people. This protection of people is considered as the primordial responsibility of a leader. Isn't that still relevant? And who was instrumental in making Rāmā recognise that responsibility? As a royal lady (princess/queen), Sītā never shirked from her responsibility to prompt SriRāmā to follow what was the righteous path. In fact, for the same reason, King Janaka of Mithila, the father of Sītā, says this statement to SriRāmā on Sītā-Rāmā's wedding –

īyañ sītā mama sutā sahadharmacārī tava.

praṭiccha cainān bhadrañ tē pāṇiñ grhṇīṣva pāṇinā ॥²

Meaning— “O! Rāmā! Take my daughter's hand in marriage, she will be in unison with you, in your path of righteousness”. The very special added meaning to this sloka is that “Rāmā... If at all you fail to perform your duties, *Sītā will herself go a step ahead of you and show you the path of Dharma (righteousness)*”. These were not mere words of theory by Janaka. It was practised by Sītā on the announcement of Exile to Rāmā by Daśarathā through the stepmother Kaikēyī. Rāmā wanted Sītā to stay back in the royal house, while he was the only one instructed to spend the hard times in the forest for 14 years. This was Rāmā's idea. But Sītā was not going to give in so easily; she decided to accompany Rāmā at all odds. Was this any sign of male chauvinism by SriRāmā? Rather he wished comfort for Sītā. It was Sītā's freedom and independence that was insisted time and again in all the incidents right from choosing to go to forest with Rāmā till advising him on protecting the sages. If at all, anyone wants to proclaim that she suffered by going to forest, it was her choice. Isn't that an outcome of her freedom to choose?

Repudiations for the previous article's statements on Sītā

1. *Prince Rāmā eventually pronounces her impure and rejects her. (Madina, E., 2023)

In the exact verses of Valmiki Rāmāyana, Rāmā does not pronounce her as impure. Even though the author (Madina, E., 2023) proclaims that she refers to the female predominant Chandrabati's version of the Rāmāyana (Chandrabati, 2020) and not from Valmiki Rāmāyana. Still, the fabrications should not be projected as truth. Rather, if a reader follows the author's view, the original happening is obscured, and truth becomes hidden by a lie that is emphasized several times. *Many such allegations hide the truth over a course of time just like how sand deposits can even hide a mountain after thousands of years.*

2. *Kamala Subramaniam writes that pain is ‘the predominant emotion in the Rāmāyana’ (Madina, E., 2023)

Rāmāyana is praised for its varied emotions. If a reader or a researcher, carefully investigates Rāmāyana, *Valour is the predominant emotion in Rāmāyana. It is the valour of Sītā like a warrior that is misunderstood as pain.* The moment some women writers claim Sītā undergoes pain, they weaken her strength as a queen like Rani Lakshmi Bai that we come across in thence Indian history. Women who are athletes or weightlifters are accoladed for their body strength. Women who strive to become political leaders or business icons are also looked upon for their mental strength. Sītā, in agreement with her times, responded back to

SriRāmā when she was given a statement of non-acceptance by Rāmā during the Agni Pareeksha context.

A. Understanding the Agni Pareeksha - What happened on the day?

It is an outcome of the very human nature of Rāmā. Rāmā himself claims that he is a human and not God in a sloka in Yuddha kānda of Śrīmad Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa.

ātamānaṁmānuṣaṁ manyē rāmaṁ daśarathātmajam ॥³

Committing an error was also a part of the human nature of Rāmā. But many times, what is not or understated is his statement after Sītā's fire test. It was this same Rāmā, who was missing her and searching for her like a crazy man in the forests after her abduction. He was clueless about what happened to her and was on the verge of giving up his own life in the absence of Sītā (Sastri, V.S.S. 1949). This was out of the excessive attachment to his spouse. Keeping that Rāmā in mind - wearing that spectacle, if an audience looks at Rāmā at the juncture of the fire test of Sītā, one can witness that, these are his exact points.

- Being the heir of his dynasty, Rāmā cannot accept back Sītā after her stay at the Ravana's.
- His immediate statement was to let her go according to her wish but not going to possess her back. (Sastri, V.S.S. 1949).
- He also adds that, his affection for Sītā has dissolved now to nothingness. This he says, to give up on her, being shackled by the norms of the citizens of his kingdom.
- The next important statement is to be highlighted. Rāmā clearly states that he is like a person with eye-disease and Sītā is like a lustre of light. It implies that Rāmā's perception and eventually his outlook is contaminated, and it is nothing with Sītā. She is as good as a lustrous light. (Sastri, V.S.S. 1949).

B. Sītā's bold stand against Rāmā's words

One thing is misunderstood with many non-indigenous readers of Rāmāyaṇa. It is Sītā who speaks out to light the pyre for her own test (Sastri, V.S.S. 1949). She claims she is the daughter of the Earth. Also adds many "if clause".

- If I am solely devoted to my husband even in his physical absence, let the fire guard me.
- If I have not crossed Rāmā, the knower of all Dharma with my deed, word and thought, may the fire guard me. (Ranganji, R. 2012)
- The Sun, Moon, directions, day, night, dawn, dusk, earth and space know that I am a woman of character. (Ranganji, R. 2012)

After all these vows, she falls even without a second thought into the fire. Fire God comes out of fire, brings back Sītā and gives her to Rāmā. Fire God advocates for Sītā's purity and testifies that she is devoid of any blemishes. These are the exact sloka words of Fire God to Rāmā. "O! Rāmā! Accept her. Talk not harshly to her. This is my command to you. (Dr. R. Rangan. 2012)

Viśuddhabhāvāṁ niṣpāpāṁ pratigrhaṇiṣva maithilīm.

na kiñcirabhīdhātavayā aham ājañāpayāmi tē ॥⁴

"Mythili (Sita) is of untainted mind and a sinless one. Take her back without any reply, I am ordering you." – says the fire god.

C. Repudiations – continued

3. *Sītā is initially presented in the Rāmāyaṇa as the 'Ur-Housewife': she embodies *Nari Dharm*, the ideal feminine code of conduct, showing endless dedica-

tion to her husband and society's expectations. However, by the end of Sītā's story and in many retellings, the notion of the perfect woman and wife is shattered. (Madina, E., 2023).

In the very example of Sītā and Rāmā, after being corrected by the fire god, Rāmā thinks of Sītā's affection for a moment, with tears in his eyes, accepts that he was indifferent to Sītā before and now he understands her. *He also emphasizes on a statement that, he was trying to do it as a responsible king to his citizens by showing Sītā's purity which will never be questioned further in the future.* Finally, he is with Sītā in front of the Fire God following his advice to accept back Sītā with grace. *He stood corrected accepting his own flaws.*

Viśuddhā triṣhu lōkēṣumaithilījanakātamaajā .
na vihātuṇ mayā śakyā kīrtirātamavatā yathā ॥⁵

"Mythili is unsullied in the three worlds. Renouncing her is not feasible just as fame and as she is like my own self."

avaśayaṇ ca mayākārayaṇ saravēṣāṇ vō vacō hitam
snighdhānān lōkanādhānām ēvaṇ ca vadatān hitam ॥⁶

"You are worship worthy of the world and loving people advising me in this way. Your words of good advice are good to all and for me. I will certainly follow." –Rama to the Fire God.

Sītā's emotions after this may not be shown in Valmiki Rāmāyana. But soon after this, her father-in-law, King Daśarathā also appears from the heaven and once again gives an unequivocal testimony to his daughter-in-law. This again proves that Rāmā and hence the Epic are not to be underestimated or disregarded for their treatment of Sītā.

Some qualities of Rama as in Srimad Valmiki Ramayana

As the article argues that Rama's actions were driven by a sense of duty and human nature rather than malice, his specific behaviours in the epic can be mapped to some of his qualities. In the *Narada-Valmiki Samvada*, that marks the very beginning of Srimad Valmiki Ramayana, a set of sixteen qualities define an "Ideal Man." The answer given by Sage Narada for that Ideal Man is *Rama*. Integrating those qualities of Rama into this analysis of the *Agni Pareeksha* or the exile can help prove that his "attachment to his spouse" was balanced with his "responsibility as a leader".

Quality (Guna)	Meaning	Application in this article
Guṇavān	Endowed with good qualities	Rama's inherent goodness acknowledged by Sita.
Vīryavān	Possessor of prowess/valour	The "predominant emotion" identified as Valour.
Dharmajñāḥ	Knower of Dharma	His commitment to the citizens' welfare.
Kṛtajñāḥ	Grateful	His eventual recognition and acceptance of Sītā's purity after the fire test
Satyavākyaḥ	Speaker of truth	His adherence to the promise given to the sages.
Dṛḍhavrataḥ	Resolute in vows	His steadfastness in the path of Dharma regardless of pain.
Cāritreṇa yuktaḥ	Of good conduct	Supporting the "Ur-Housewife" vs "Ur-Husband" dynamic.
Sarvabhūtahite rataḥ	Devoted to the welfare of all	His focus on the kingdom's welfare over personal attachment.

Sītā - A Perfect woman!

Advocating feminist reviews, the previous literature picturizes that Sītā tries to exhibit the qualities of a perfect woman. It's certainly a "No". This is because, she was possessing good qualities inherently. In her ways of moving with the world, she never made any deliberate "attempt" to be an ideal woman. She naturally possessed some or even many good qualities. Further in many incidents, she exhibited a very normal and moderate behaviour, in incidents such as arguing with Rāmā to go along with him to the forests, mocking at Rāmā at a playful swimming competition with him, desiring for a golden deer to play with, expressing fear and despair to Hanumān when in Aśōka Vanā, marked by many slokas of many kāndas in the Indian Epic Śrīmad Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa.

Sītā as a "Sahadharmacarī" (Partner in Righteousness)

Sītā's role was not passive. In the *Aranya Kanda*, she mentors Rāmā, reminding him of his duties to protect the sages. This aligns with King Janaka's declaration during their marriage: "*Iyam Sītā mama sutā sahadharmacarī tava*". This implies that Sītā would act as a guide should Rāmā ever falter in his path of *Dharma*. Her choice to accompany Rāmā into exile was not a sign of submission but an exercise of her freedom to choose and her commitment to their shared path.

The Paradigm of Leadership

Sītā is portrayed as a strong-minded woman with clarity regarding her duties as a Princess and a leader. Her decisions were not a result of external pressure but were conscious choices made to serve as a moral example for the citizens.

Traditional Dharma Framework	Modern Individualistic Framework
Focus on Interdependence and Co-existence	Focus on Hyper-independence
Sacrifice as a Price of Leadership	Sacrifice as a Sign of Ill-treatment
Mutual Accountability (<i>Sahadharmacarī</i>)	Adversarial Gender Dynamics

Sītā's acceptance of the "fire test" (*Agni Pareeksha*) can be compared to a modern leader's professional accountability. It was a "moral agreement" signed for the welfare of the kingdom, carrying a psychological price for both Sītā and Rāmā.

Re-evaluating Modern Societal Challenges - It is a torment!

While contemporary modernization often emphasizes individual financial independence and personal ego, it sometimes overlooks the value of the family system. The hard truth of adulthood involves recognizing that basic life management and care for others are universal responsibilities, regardless of gender. A healthy society requires a revival of thought where *Nāri Dharma* (rights and duties of women) is complemented by *Purusha Dharma* (rights and duties of men).

Implications for Practice

This work highlights the importance of interpreting the Indian epic Śrīmad Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa in its original ethical and cultural contexts rather than through imposed modern ideological lenses. The mutual understanding between Rāmā and Sītā offers a practical model of relationships grounded in shared responsibility, moral accountability, self-restraint, and reciprocal respect. For educators, scholars, and social commentators, this perspective encourages balanced discussions on gender and family dynamics that value dialogue and ethical conduct over adversarial interpretations. Such an approach can support more constructive engagement with issues of partnership, leadership, and social values in contemporary society.

- **Ethical Interdependence:** This relationship model prioritizes co-existence over hyper-independence, suggesting that healthy partnerships are "watered and nourished" through mutual respect rather than adversarial conflict.
- **The Price of Quality:** Rāmā's commitment required him to prioritize his duty to the state over his personal attachment to Sītā, a burden that both partners understood as the price of their leadership.
- **Contemporary Relevance:** For modern educators and social commentators, this perspective offers a way to view gender dynamics through the lens of shared responsibility (*Nāri Dharma* complemented by *Purusha Dharma*) rather than a struggle for power.

Conclusion

Human beings are social animals. At least, most of them cannot be independent, rather only inter-dependent. That's why it is seen even in today's world, a major lot of divorcees or widowers need a companion after some time, if not, at least a family to hold on to. Emotions cannot be aimed at emptiness. An organized relationship is far better than a random one. This paved way to the early man, to form a family system. The negated statements of the previous article only encourage the world to move apart. This is happily accepted by women in the name of independence. What happens in independence is a frustration of reaching an emptiness. Even though a marriage system comes with its own cons, Nāri Dharm(righteous norms for women) ought to be complimented by Nar-Dharm / Purusha-Dharm (righteous norms for men) – That becomes the ethics of a man too. This article attempted to give valid arguments of how Rāmā revered Sītā in many incidents. Also, on how the decisions of Sītā have a fair reason in every such incident. Only in such mutual understandings and mutual respect, is a relationship watered and nourished.

Endnotes

1. *Srimad Vālmikī Ramayana, Sundarakāṇḍa, 38th Sarga – 41st Śloka (5.38.41)*
2. *Srimad Vālmikī Ramayana, Bālakāṇḍa, 73rd Sarga – 27th Śloka (1.73.27)*
3. *Srimad Vālmikī Ramayana, Yuddhakāṇḍa, 120th Sarga – 11th Śloka (6.120.11)*
4. *Srimad Vālmikī Ramayana, Yuddhakāṇḍa, 121st Sarga – 10th Śloka (6.121.10)*
5. *Srimad Vālmikī Ramayana, Yuddhakāṇḍa, 121st Sarga – 20th Śloka (6.121.20)*
6. *Srimad Vālmikī Ramayana, Yuddhakāṇḍa, 121st Sarga – 21st Śloka (6.121.21)*

Bibliography

- Vālmikī. *Srimad Vālmikī Rāmāyaṇa*. Edited by K. S. Krishnaswami Sastrigal and V. H. Subrahmanya Sastri, K. Press, 1933.
- *Srimad Vālmikī Rāmāyaṇa - Original Devanagari Verses and Roman Transliteration*. IIT Kanpur, www.valmiki.iitk.ac.in. Accessed 21 Apr. 2026.
- Gīta Press. *The Rāmāyaṇa of Vālmikī (Sanskrit Text and English Translation)*. 3rd ed., 2 vols., Gita Press, 2020.
- Ranganji, R. *The Ramayana of Valmiki – Critical Edition*. WEBOLIM, 2012.
- Sastri, V. S. S. *Lectures on the Ramayana*. Madras Samskrit Academy, 1949.
- Madina, E. "Mythology and Reality: TV-Storytelling and Feminist Agency in the Rāmāyaṇa and *The Real Housewives*." *Feminist Review*, vol. 134, no. 1, 2023.
- Chandrabati. *Chandrabati's Ramayan*. Translated by Nabaneeta Dev Sen, Zubaan, 2020.